

Report of the 19th Plenary of the RDA, June 2022

Report contributors

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Introduction

This document has been prepared by [ELIXIR's RDA Activities Focus Group](#) to showcase the synergies and activities of the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#) which may be useful for ELIXIR members operating in the life sciences domain. The RDA was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data. The ELIXIR RDA Activities Focus Group has prepared eighteen reports of [RDA Plenary events](#) to date containing overviews of highlighted RDA recommendations and outputs. This report contains highlights from various sessions of the RDA 19th Plenary which took place as a hybrid event in South Korea, 20-23 June, 2022. Additional links to collaborative note documents and/or abstracts provided by the breakout session chairs are included.

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About the 19th RDA Plenary

The nineteenth RDA Plenary was the first RDA Plenary to be held as a fully hybrid event with virtual and onsite participants interacting and accessing recordings of all sessions using the [Whova](#) conferencing platform. It was combined with [SciDataCon](#) and organised as the third [International Data Week](#) in Seoul, South Korea in June, 2022.

The organisers reported impressive engagement in this year's event:

- 827 participants (182 onsite, 645 virtual).
- Attendance from 50 countries.
- 8 Plenary meetings.
- 73 RDA breakout sessions.
- 47 SciDataCon sessions.

The overall conference theme was “**Data to Improve Our World**” and the plenary sessions highlighted a diverse range of topics such as the role of data in addressing global challenges, the state of open science and reproducibility, citizen science and the needs for data science and stewardship education. The RDA breakout sessions and SciDataCon parallel sessions were organised into seven blocks distributed over four days.

Following this year's successful event the upcoming 20th RDA Plenary will mark the organisation's ten year anniversary and be a hybrid event with onsite activities in [Gothenburg, Sweden on 21-23 March 2023](#). Subsequent to this the upcoming 4th International Data Week will co-locate with the 21st RDA Plenary with SciDataCon 2023 and takes place in [Salzburg, Austria on 23–26 October 2023](#).

RDA Group Acronyms

- Working Group - WG
- Interest Group - IG
- Birds of Feather - BoF
- Community of Practice - CoP

Summaries Section

This section contains shorter highlight recommendations from the event and other key links and information from the various RDA 19th Plenary sessions.

[Highlighted RDA recommendations & outputs](#)

- Curating for FAIR and Reproducible Research (CURE-FAIR) - WG
- Persistent Identification of Instruments - WG
- Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies (I-ADOPT) - WG
- COVID-19 - WG
- FAIR 4 Research Software (FAIR4RS) - WG

[ELIXIR in RDA breakout sessions](#)

- Discipline Focused Data Issues
- Defining, managing, and reporting dataset quality in a multidisciplinary Open Data space
- Data Infrastructures and Environments – Regional/Disciplinary, Institutional, International
- Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning
- Semantics, Ontology, Standardisation
- Data Lifecycles - Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward
- FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Principles, Adoption, Implementation, and Deployment

[ELIXIR in SciDataCon parallel sessions](#)

- Supporting Research Transparency, Accountability, and Reproducibility: Lessons from the Trenches
- Where are the vocabularies that make environmental datasets FAIR?
- Scientific Vocabularies: needs, status, validity, governance and sustainability
- Practical Cross-Domain Data Sharing: Envisioning a Core Interoperability Framework

Highlighted RDA recommendations & outputs - Summary

RDA Recommendations are “flagship” outputs of the RDA and can include a broad range of documents including specifications, taxonomies, workflows etc. They are produced by Working Groups (WG) and undergo a formal review process before they are endorsed. *RDA Supporting outputs* are educational and informative documents that undergo a lighter community review process, such as RDA-branded guidelines, brochures and whitepapers etc. This section covers some of the recommendations and outputs that were highlighted during the plenary.

Curating for FAIR and Reproducible Research (CURE-FAIR) WG

The aim of the WG was to establish standards-based guidelines for curating for reproducible and FAIR data and code.

- **Recommendation: 10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research,**
<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00074>
This document offers a framework for implementing effective curation workflows for achieving greater FAIR-ness and long-term usability of research data and code. Adoption of the guidelines for curating reproducible and FAIR research will improve the prospects for a reproducible scholarly record.
- **Supporting output: Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output,**
<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00063>
This report identifies a set of key challenges associated with generating, sharing, and using reproducible computation-based scientific results.

Persistent Identification of Instruments WG

The aim of the WG was to establish a cross-discipline, operational solution for the unique and lasting identification of measuring instruments actively operated in the sciences.

- **Recommendation: Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instrument,**
<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00070>
This is the recommended schema for the persistent identification of instruments by institutions or bodies using or managing instruments. The Schema is PID provider independent and has been tested with ePIC and DataCite by numerous institutions including Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie GmbH, British Oceanographic Data Centre, EUDAT.
- **Supporting output: Persistent Identification of Instruments,**
<http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-018>
This document provides two tested approaches for persistent identification of instruments.

Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies (I-ADOPT) WG

The aim of the WG was to create a community-agreed framework for representing observable properties by bringing together groups that have been working on developing terminologies to accurately encode what was measured, observed, derived, or computed.

- **Recommendation: Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies (I-ADOPT) WG Outputs and Recommendations,**

<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00071>

This document proposes a way of systematically decomposing variable descriptions into a machine and human readable format and includes references to 6 supporting outputs:

- Catalogue of terminologies
- I-ADOPT Variable Design Patterns (VDPs)
- Step-by-step guide for Minting new Variables
- Alignments to other ontological frameworks
- Guidelines for use-case specific scenarios
- Applications

COVID-19 WG

The WGs guidelines aim at developing a system for data sharing in public health emergencies that supports scientific research and policy making, including an overarching framework, common tools and processes, and principles that can be embedded in research practice.

- **Recommendation: RDA COVID-19 Recommendations and Guidelines,**

<https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00052>

This document is a body of work that comprises how data from multiple disciplines inform response to a pandemic combined with guidelines and recommendations on data sharing under COVID-19 circumstances.

- **Supporting output: RDA COVID-19 Zotero Library,**

<https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00051>

This document was created to support development of the RDA-COVID19 Data Sharing Recommendations and Guidelines for the following focus areas: clinical, community, epidemiology, Indigenous, legal and ethics, omics, social, and software.

- **Supporting output: Sharing COVID-19 Epidemiology Data,**

<https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00049>

This document provides supplemental resources, and further develops the global data-driven vision described in the guidelines. This includes a proposed computable framework to support system responses for emerging pathogens. It offers compatible and reliable data models, protocols, and action plans for newly identified threats such as COVID-19.

FAIR 4 Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG

The aim of the WG was to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of research software by developing and promoting a set of FAIR Guiding Principles for software—addressing specific characteristics of software, such as its executability, composite nature, and continuous evolution and versioning.

- **Recommendation: FAIR Principles for Research Software,**

<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>

This document adapts some of the FAIR principles to improve the sharing and reuse of research software. Supporting research reproducibility for research organisations, better practices and more software usage for its developers, clarity for funders around their own policies and requirements for software investments, and guidelines for publishers on sharing requirements.

ELIXIR in RDA breakout sessions - Summary

Breakout sessions are proposed by a Working Group (WG), an Interest Group (IG), a Community of Practice (CoP), jointly by multiple groups, or by an individual member. WG, IG, CoP and joint meeting sessions are typically interactive and informational—presenting objectives and progress updates, collaborating on next steps regarding adoption and other related activities. Birds of a Feather (BoF) sessions covers topics that could be recommended for the creation of new WGs/IGs.

The sessions were distributed over 7 blocks of parallel sessions and organised into one or more [Plenary Pathways](#) to highlight convergences, and to propose divergences that participants may not have considered. This section highlights some of the topics covered by the reports from 18 of the RDA breakout sessions attended under each pathway.

Discipline Focused Data Issues

- [Life Science Data worldwide](#) (RDA Breakout 4)
This IG session focused on bridging between life science data infrastructures in different regions of the world and relevant RDA groups. It was organised by the *Life Science Data Infrastructures IG* to announce its change in name (previously ELIXIR Bridging Force IG) and scope.

Highlight: Presentations of the participating infrastructures H₃ABioNet, ELIXIR, US NIH Office of Data Science Strategy, US DOE Office of Science, Australian BioCommons and RDA engagements. “FAIR for infrastructure” was proposed as a topic for upcoming activities.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE) and Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR)

FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Principles, Adoption, Implementation, and Deployment

- [Supporting FAIR in software](#) (RDA Breakout 5)
This joint session focused on software citation and how best to support the use of software in research, in terms of recognising it, managing it, citing it, sharing it and making sure there are best practices in place that meet the needs of different disciplines and communities. It was organised jointly by the *RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) WG*, the *FAIR for Research Software WG* and the *Software Source Code IG* to support knowledge exchange and collaboration between the groups.

Report by Marek Suchánek (ELIXIR-CZ)

- [FAIR4RS - FAIR principles for research software outcomes and governance](#) (RDA Breakout 4)
This WG session presented outputs that support the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of research software. It was organised by *FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG* to present and promote the WGs final outcomes—including the RDA endorsed recommendation *FAIR principles for research software* (2022), supporting outputs, adoption guidance, and future governance arrangements.

Report by Fotis Psomopoulos (ELIXIR-GR)

- [The FAIR Data Maturity Model in practice: learning from adoption](#) (RDA Breakout 6)
This WG session focused on assessment criteria for FAIRness and a model for measuring the maturity level of a dataset. It was organised by the *FAIR Data Maturity Model WG* to collect lessons learned from adopting and implementing the RDA endorsed recommendation *FAIR Data Maturity Model* (2020).

Highlight: The EOSC FAIR metrics and Data Quality Task Force (lead Mark Wilkinson) is to publish a white paper for review.

Report by Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR)

- [Defining, managing, and reporting dataset quality in a multidisciplinary Open Data space](#) (RDA Breakout 2)
This BoF session focused on managing and communicating dataset quality information in diverse scientific and multidisciplinary environments. It was organised by the EOSC Task Force on FAIR metrics and Data Quality to get a broad overview of related challenges, needs and interests that could underpin the forming of a new RDA Working Group.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

Data Infrastructures and Environments - Regional/Disciplinary, Institutional, International

- [Data Repository Attributes Working Group \(DRAWG\) Launch Meeting](#) (RDA Breakout 5)
This WG session focused on metadata and interoperability of research data repositories. It was organised by the *Data Repository Attributes WG* as its first plenary meeting to 1) introduce and discuss the work being undertaken by the group; 2) identify and engage new stakeholders and potential members; and 3) share and get broader input on the early, draft work of the group from our first three months.

Report by Allyson Lister (ELIXIR-UK)

- [Global Open Research Commons \(GORC\) IG update and GORC International Model WG: Reflections and Document Development](#) (RDA Breakout 5)
This joint session focused on global interoperability for research outputs and services across disciplines. It was organised by the *GORC International Model WG* to provide updates on and to discuss the future steps towards identifying attributes that would be expected by users and needed for interoperability across infrastructures.

Highlight: Promising work towards converging on a typology and concise set of definitions for the essential elements of a Research Commons. Input being provided by several pan-national, domain focused and national commons—such as EOSC, NeIC (Nordics), IVOA (astronomy), CCADI (arctic data), AARDC (Australia), CSTCloud (China), KISTI (South Korea), NII Research Data Cloud (Japan), The Alliance (Canada) etc.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

- [A Fabric for FAIR Digital Objects](#) (RDA Breakout 5)
This IG session focused on FAIR Digital Objects (FDO)—virtual data objects that may represent data, software, or other research resources—as a means to facilitate findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (FAIR) in data infrastructures. It was organised by the *FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG* to update the RDA Community with ongoing work in the FDO communities and related RDA groups.

Highlight: 1st International Conference on FAIR Digital Objects, 26–28 October, Leiden, The Netherlands. The conference main outputs will include the first international declaration of coalition members on FAIR Digital Objects, the *Leiden Declaration on FAIR Digital Objects*.

Report by Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR)

- [Electronic Laboratory Notebooks | Challenges and steps to solutions](#) (RDA Breakout 3)
This BoF session focused on challenges related to providing organisation-wide electronic laboratory notebooks. It was organised by the *Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG* to bring together people confronted with the challenges to find next steps towards solutions.

Report by Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR)

Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning

- [Early Careers' engagement: supporting data conversations and capacity building](#) (RDA Breakout 2)
This IG session focused on networking and mentoring for early and mid-career researchers and professionals. It was organised by the *Early Career and Engagement IG* to present the ECEIG Mentoring Programme, to facilitate networking and to engage the group of mentors and mentees.

Report by Fotis Psomopoulos (ELIXIR-GR)

- [Discipline-specific Guidance for DMPs](#) (RDA Breakout 7)
This WG session focused on how discipline-specific guidance and templates for DMPs should address shortcomings and improve FAIR data outputs. It was organised by the *Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG* to present the results of a survey and to discuss different aspects of the topic.

Report by Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR)

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#) (RDA Breakout 6)
This WG session presented outputs that support curation activities for reproducible and FAIR data and code. It was organised by the *CURE-FAIR WG* to present and promote the WGs final outcomes—including the RDA endorsed recommendation *10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research* (2022), supporting outputs, and adoption guidance.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

- [Professionalising Data Stewardship | Global Updates and RDA PDS Effort Planning](#) (RDA Breakout 1)
This IG session focused on all aspects of professionalising data stewardship—including business cases, organisational models, career tracks, and training. It was organised by the *Professionalising Data Stewardship IG* to highlight recent outputs and upcoming opportunities for consultation or collaboration between members of its task groups, EOSC task forces and the wider RDA community.

Highlight: Celia van Gelder (ELIXIR-NL) presented on behalf of EOSC Association’s Task Force on Data stewardship, curricula and career paths. Members of the IG are exploring several aspects of data stewardship including a research landscape of data stewardship training.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

Semantics, Ontology, Standardisation

- [What is going on in VSSIG \(Vocabulary Services IG\)?](#) (RDA Breakout 3)
This IG session focused on community-based recommendations for publishing controlled vocabularies on the web and in particular on metadata and interoperable variable descriptions. It was organised by the *Vocabulary Services IG* to present updates and get feedback on ongoing and proposed future work including minimum common metadata for semantic artefacts, forming a WG on FAIR Semantics and the RDA endorsed recommendation *Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies (I-ADOPT) WG Outputs and Recommendations* (2022).

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

- [Beyond machine-actionable DMPs - let's go forward together!](#) (RDA Breakout 1)
This joint session focused on recent developments in machine-actionable DMPs. It was organised by the *Active DMP IG* and the *DMP Common Standard WG* to provide updates on the RDA endorsed recommendation *RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans* (2020) and to identify new areas that require coordinated action.

Report by Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR) & Marek Suchánek (ELIXIR-CZ)

- [A shared understanding of Sensitive Data: an update on current progress and looking to future work](#) (RDA Breakout 2)
This IG session focused on challenges and solutions in working with sensitive data across disciplines and regions. It was organised by the *Sensitive Data Interest Group* to share experiences, present preliminary findings and plan next steps for IG outputs.

Report by Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR)

- [BoF - Is FAIR FAIR? A discussion of the overlaps in the FAIR principles of data management and AI-Readiness](#) (RDA Breakout 6)
This BoF session focused on the questions of how fully aligned the FAIR principles are with the concept of AI-readiness (Is FAIR FAIR?) and to highlight potential extensions necessary in the AI sub-domains identified to achieve both FAIRness and AI-readiness. It was organised to bring together existing RDA groups in a discussion on the topic.

Report by Fotis Psomopoulos (ELIXIR-GR)

Data Lifecycles - Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward

- [Searching for connections: Data search, web search and literature search](#) (RDA Breakout 3)
This IG session focused on data discovery and search across resource types, repositories and users. It was organised by *Data Discovery Paradigms IG* to share relevant updates on the topic and identify a work plan towards a best practices output.

Report by Marek Suchánek (ELIXIR-CZ)

The sessions covered by this report were organised by the following RDA groups:

- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [Sensitive Data IG](#)
- [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG](#)

- [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#)
- [DMP Common Standards WG](#)
- [Active Data Management Plans IG](#)
- [Early Career and Engagement IG](#)
- [Vocabulary Services IG](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR₄RS\) WG](#)
- [GORC \(Global Open Research Commons\) International Model WG](#)
- [RDA/WDS \(World Data Systems\) Scholarly Link Exchange \(Scholix\) WG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR₄RS\) WG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [Data Repository Attributes WG](#)
- [CURE-FAIR \(Curating for FAIR and Reproducible Research\) WG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)

ELIXIR in SciDataCon parallel sessions - Summary

SciDataCon sessions are peer-reviewed research and practice presentations, which cover all aspects of the role of data in research, society and policy.

- [Supporting Research Transparency, Accountability, and Reproducibility: Lessons from the Trenches \(317\)](#)

The aim of this session was to explore how different groups have been working to ensure that research results are computationally reproducible by taking steps to prevent digital obsolescence of the supporting data and code.

Highlight: Examples of how to offer support to researchers in assessing and improving computational interoperability through code review services, knowledge exchange and policy.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

- [Where are the vocabularies that make environmental datasets FAIR? \(428\)](#)

The aim of this session was to identify challenges and solutions to adopting and promoting vocabularies that are controlled, standardised, and persistent (5+ years into the future) to maintain integrity of datasets in the environmental and earth sciences.

Highlight: Good selection of talks addressing the topic in a way that translates easily to other domains. Complex experimental variables can be described using ontologies and frameworks such as I-ADOPT to improve interoperability. Research Vocabularies Australia is currently working to provide domain/community guidance to help researchers determine which term from what vocabulary to use.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

- [Scientific Vocabularies: needs, status, validity, governance and sustainability \(461\)](#)

The aim of this session was to address governance concerns related to scientific vocabularies and how to encode information related to governance as metadata to support vocabulary assessment and selection.

Highlight: Allyson Lister (ELIXIR-UK) presented on [Scientific Vocabularies: needs, status, validity, governance and sustainability \(slides\)](#). She described the role of ontologies and their governance within FAIRsharing and the Community Curation Programme, which is part of the EOSC Future / RDA Domain Ambassador programme of which she is a part.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE) & Report by Allyson Lister (ELIXIR-UK)

- [Practical Cross-Domain Data Sharing: Envisioning a Core Interoperability Framework \(438\)](#)
The aim of this session was to highlight some of the work that has been done in building a cross-domain interoperability layer on top of the FAIR Digital Object Framework and to suggest a path forward.

Highlight: The 2-year EC funded *WorldFAIR: Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice* project will focus on 11 domain and cross-domain case studies to address challenges in interoperability within disciplines and for interdisciplinary research. The case studies will develop FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and test the ideas outlined in the session.

Report by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE)

Detailed Reports Section

This section contains detailed reports and key links from the various conference sessions.

- [RDA Breakout 1](#)
 - Beyond machine-actionable DMPs - let's go forward together!
 - Professionalising Data Stewardship | Global Updates and RDA PDS Effort Planning
- [RDA Breakout 2](#)
 - Defining, managing, and reporting dataset quality in a multidisciplinary Open Data space
 - A shared understanding of Sensitive Data: an update on current progress and looking to future work
 - Early Careers' engagement: supporting data conversations and capacity building
- [RDA Breakout 3](#)
 - What is going on in VSSIG?
 - Searching for connections: Data search, web search and literature search
 - Electronic Laboratory Notebooks | Challenges and steps to solutions
- [RDA Breakout 4](#)
 - Life Science Data worldwide
 - FAIR4RS - FAIR principles for research software outcomes and governance
- [RDA Breakout 5](#)
 - Global Open Research Commons IG update and GORC International Model WG: Reflections and Document Development
 - A Fabric for FAIR Digital Objects
 - Supporting FAIR in software
 - Data Repository Attributes Working Group (DRAWG) Launch Meeting
- [RDA Breakout 6](#)
 - 10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research
 - Is FAIR FAIR? A discussion of the overlaps in the FAIR principles of data management and AI-Readiness
 - The FAIR Data Maturity Model in practice: learning from adoption
- [RDA Breakout 7](#)
 - Discipline-specific Guidance for Data WG Discipline-specific Guidance for DMPs
- [SciDataCon Sessions](#)
 - Supporting Research Transparency, Accountability, and Reproducibility: Lessons from the Trenches
 - Where are the vocabularies that make environmental datasets FAIR?
 - Scientific Vocabularies: needs, status, validity, governance and sustainability
 - Practical Cross-Domain Data Sharing: Envisioning a Core Interoperability Framework

RDA Breakout 1

Joint session: WG DMP Common Standards WG, IG Active Data Management Plans IG: *Beyond machine-actionable DMPs - let's go forward together!*

Reported by Paulette Lieby and Marek Suchánek: ([Collaborative notes](#))

Paulette Lieby

- Two groups: DMP CS WG which is in maintenance mode, and Active DMPs IG: all topics related to maDMPs
- 2019: RDA DMP Common Standards published: <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard>
- maDMPs are living documents through automated updating; they require a well-defined workflow within a DM infrastructure (information exchange), and a common information exchange standard (see previous point)
- maDMPs are the glue between connected systems
- Two adoption stories presented (both open source tools)
 1. ARGOS Elli Papadopoulou GR
 - Integrates data services and WFs
 - All disciplines and all types of research outputs
 2. DAMAP, TU Vienna (demo)
 - Integrates with university ecosystem: data and computer services, CRIS
- Open discussion:
 - Future directions? What kind of conversation could we lead, instigate?
 - 1) PID integration; connecting to CRIS, learning from repositories
 - 2) which info would be reusable from one DMP to the next?
 - maDMP to be queried and compliance evaluated with funders requirements
 - The issue of using so many diverse tools (plus: DMP OPIDoR, DSW, DMPonline, etc....)
 - Not considered a problem: on the contrary, it strengthens the community by helping disseminate, and anchor DMP practice
 - However, RDA CS by itself does not guarantee interoperability, so one must always be vigilant
 - Create a DMP commons? As a way to exchange informations, but not as a map of system data organisation
- Maintenance of the recommendation
 - If in the future the CS needs a rewrite, this is outside the maintenance WG's scope (as needs more wo-manpower)
- Election of co-chairs

Marek Suchánek:

The session was chaired by Tomasz Miksa who is co-chair of both Active DMPs IG and DMP Common Standards WG. Tomasz explained the outline of the session and also introduced both IG and WG for newcomers. Both IG and WG deal with machine-actionable DMPs and the related DMP Common Standard which is now in maintenance mode. Several DMP tools adopted the standard and there are several plans how to continue (e.g. funder extensions). The activity around the DMP Common Standard can be followed in its [GitHub repository](#).

Presentations of adoption stories followed, planned were three presentations but Claire Austin (who works on government-related extension of the DMP Common Standard) unfortunately didn't attend the session. Elli Papadopoulou presented ARGOS (DMP tool related to OpenAIRE and EOSC based on OpenDMP) and its features with respect to maDMPs. Then, Tomasz presented a new DMP open-source tool called DAMAP developed at TU Vienna that is tightly integrated with other systems, e.g. to link projects, people, datasets, and storages.

A brief open discussion brought up several interesting ideas that will probably be taken into consideration by IG and WG, e.g. DMP as FDO, DMP commons, or PID integration. WG may update the DMP Common Standard based on the current community needs. After the discussion, the last point on the agenda was the election of new co-chairs (replacements for those who step down) – 2 for IG and 1 for WG. There were candidates in the audience; however, it was decided to do the election another time with a broader audience.

[IG Professionalising Data Stewardship IG: Professionalising Data Stewardship | Global Updates and RDA PDS Effort Planning](#)

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~21 participants

The aim of this session was to share brief updates from the teams working on different topics in the interest group and from the related EOSC Association task force. The session also aimed to identify new tasks and collaborations going forward.

Professionalising Data Stewardship (PDS-IG) has been an RDA Interest Group since 2020 and focuses on issues in building Data Stewardship (DS) capacity leading to difficulties in defining recruitment procedures and career paths. Sessions at all RDA Plenaries since RDA 14th Plenary (BoF sessions at 14th and 15th), writing the charter, forming 9 Task Groups (TG) working at and between plenaries to address topics ranging from surveying business cases for DS to job profiles, terminology in DS, models for DS, training, career track, and more. This session provides updates from 6 of the task groups and related work in one of the EOSC Association's Task Forces (EOSC TF).

The session was introduced with a reference to a [pre-recorded update on the global state of Data Stewardship by Stefan Frost](#) at the Govt Lab in New York, where he introduced 5 reimagined DS competencies to accelerate data collaborations. 1. *Stewarding data* in a responsible way includes describing and marking data discoverable, user friendly and reusable as well as matching data with research questions. 2. *Stewarding partnerships* includes bringing together widely distributed and

diverse data by enabling sophisticated data partnerships to provide access through data sharing agreements, infrastructures etc. 3. *Stewarding internal resources & processes* includes the work to bring together and align various internal interests to unlock data for or formulate the questions to address—ultimately if no one owns the process of aligning internal interests and processes making requests for and providing access to data and resources becomes hard. 4. *Stewarding sustainability* includes having financially sustainable and long term perspectives on how to provide access to certain kinds of data sets. 5. *Stewarding insights* includes thinking about how to make sure that actions and decisions are made based on insights generated from the data. Stefan concluded by asserting that these are the five elements that will make a difference.

The PDS-IG Business Case TG 1 works towards providing a short report with case studies that highlight the benefits of having DS expertise and the risks of not having it to stakeholders. Currently working on [a draft of the report](#) and incorporating outputs from the other task groups, looking for more people to get involved and considering forming a formal RDA working group to continue.

The PDS-IG Data Stewardship Models TG 3 works towards providing a model of different DS roles in particular services and organisational contexts and describing how they interact with their respective target communities. Currently developed a conceptual diagram, [conducted a survey](#) with [136 responses](#) ([82 complete](#) identifying 2 main cohorts—1. libraries/advisory and 2. technical infrastructure—and a clear bias towards European respondents—where the group speculated that the bias could be due to the term “data stewardship” being more established in Europe. The group plans to reach out to identify specific communities to get better representation, follow up with in-depth interviews with selected respondents and continue analysis of the current results.

[EOSC TF Data stewardship, curricula and career paths](#) works towards a common curriculum for DS skills and possibilities for career paths including DS roles and core activities. It is a relatively small TF with 20 members representing all categories of stakeholders but at the same time actively looking for more members. Working on identifying stakeholders and related initiatives and to report on how DS roles map in an international, disciplinary and institutional context. Actively seeking to align with other [EOSC-A Task forces](#), RDA [PDS-IG](#) and [Education and Training on Handling of Research Data IG](#), and any initiatives or projects implementing recommendations from the [Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science report](#).

The PDS-IG Research landscape of data stewardship training TG 5 works toward identifying gaps and needs for training in data stewardship. Currently working on [a report based on a literature review](#) that will inform the PDS-IG’s future work with three take home messages 1. Collaborate internationally on certified training including highlighting/addressing interdisciplinary differences, 2. Enable researchers to share their data from the planning stage of their project also including how to share data internally (within organisation/project) and externally, ethical and technical aspects as well as societal and practical benefits, and 3. Address the increased need for technical skills in data stewardship including

how to support [Open Science and FAIR](#). Feedback is requested on uses for the report and its findings and user communities that might benefit from reading it. Plan to look into what other outputs the TG can contribute to very shortly.

The PDS-IG Data Steward Career Tracks TG 6 works towards providing an overview of career perspectives in DS with insightful case studies. Currently working on distributing and getting respondents to the [Data Steward Career Tracks Survey](#) (launched at the plenary session and open 2–3 months).

The PDS-IG Terminology and multilingual challenges TG 2 works to provide a DS terminology tool to share and validate terms with an initial list of common terms. Currently identified challenges for translators and for databases presented as [a poster at this plenary](#).

The session concluded with ideation and discussion in breakout rooms and a full group wrap-up to identify potential RDA outputs, collaboration opportunities, milestones for the next 18 months, contributors and working groups.

RDA Breakout 2

[BoF - Defining, managing, and reporting dataset quality in a multidisciplinary Open Data space](#)

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~30 participants

The aim of this session was to provide a broad overview of how data quality information is represented and related challenges, needs and interests that could underpin the forming of a new RDA Working Group.

The session was introduced by stressing that the dataset quality is not the same as data quality and that both should be addressed. Quality information includes issues with instruments, variables and corresponding measurements, their use, etc through the entire lifecycle. Quality of input/output, metadata/docs, software/workflows, processes etc. The session included a summary from a BoF session from the 18th Plenary, 4 case studies on needs/challenges, and an overview of guidelines from the international Earth Sciences community.

[RDA-P18 BoF session "Representing and Communicating Data Quality Information"](#) included presentations on challenges and best practices from genomics, astronomy, social sciences and earth sciences as well as survey/use cases on environmental data and geospatial data. Disciplines are unique but need and challenges may be cross-disciplinary, there is an interest in learning/sharing knowledge & best-practice across disciplines, and there was an interest in working on this in the context of RDA.

Data quality in the EU-INSPIRE regulation: The first case study presented the lessons learned from the legal requirements and implementation in the [INSPIRE infrastructure for spatial information](#) from member states' public authorities in Europe. Includes a legal framework on what member states must implement (INSPIRE directive) and a technical framework with recommendations on how to implement the required components. The frameworks are based on normative references including directives & regulation as well as ISO standards and [abstract and executable test suites](#) were developed to ensure data & service conformance. Data is harvested from national catalogues to be validated and incorporated into the [INSPIRE Geportal](#), quality indicators based on the validation are accessible to the data providers. The [INSPIRE registry](#) is an ISO 19135-1:2015 (Geo info—procedures for item registration) compliant multilingual European vocabulary service to overcome the semantic aspects of data interoperability, allowing registration and linking of more specific terms in local vocabularies to harmonised terms in INSPIRE. Implementation of quality monitoring is a marathon (5+ years in INSPIRE). A huge framework requires a lot of work to incorporate changes.

Data quality and digitised documents: The second case study presented examples from digital humanities using digitised texts that have been produced using Optical Character Recognition (OCR). OCR is a tool and the digitisation is not error free and quality information is often not published with

the extracted texts. This is a problem since the errors can introduce bias and other quality issues that will influence the validity of the insight generated from the texts in scientific analyses. The speaker encourages further explorations to identify relevant assessment parameters and what quality information would be necessary in this context

Data quality to ensure unbiased AI algorithms: The third case study presented some of the [requirements of trustworthy AI](#) and fairness metrics related to training data. High quality data without biases is essential when training a decision model that is expected to make fair decisions but there are contradictory concepts of fairness—a population as a group treated equally (e.g., male / female) vs each individual—and in potential metrics to measure fairness—equality-in-outcome vs equality-in-quality approaches. No single concept of fairness and the assessment can change with regions, cultures and over time. Can be addressed by developing international quality metrics, guidelines and case studies.

Metadata standards in bioimaging: The fourth case study presentation was cancelled.

Guidelines to improve Earth science dataset quality information: The fifth case study presented an overview of international [community-based guidelines developed to improve dataset quality information](#) in the earth sciences. Dataset quality information includes whether the quality has been assessed, whether the quality is described in a way that can be understood, and ultimately whether the quality information can help in determining the usefulness of the data. The FAIR data principles can be applied/adapted to dataset quality information and the guidelines include recommendations on how to make them available—including recommended properties of structured quality assessment metrics, (meta)data schemas, and quality assessment protocols, etc. Proposed next steps include deployment across disciplines and further improvements.

The session concluded with a multidisciplinary discussion on how to continue discussions of FAIR Dataset Quality Information in the context of RDA. An RDA Group could be a place to share what is being discussed in different groups and activities across the world. An RDA Working Group (WG) would require scope and deliverable(s) for an 18 months lifetime. An RDA interest group can be a long-term place for people from different regions to meet and share. Making quality information FAIR could be a potential deliverable for a WG and the existing FAIR quality guidelines could function as a starting point for expanding to other disciplines. If focusing on a WG rather than an IG, RDA webinars could function as meeting points for the different regional initiatives, logistics could possibly be supported by the RDA Secretariat.

[IG Sensitive Data IG: A shared understanding of Sensitive Data: an update on current progress and looking to future work](#)

Reported by Paulette Lieby ([collaborative notes](#))

- The point is to come up with a shared understanding of sensitive data across geographical and disciplinary boundaries
- invited speaker: Susheel Varma UK, NHS, ELIXIR, GA4GH, UK Health Research Data Alliance, EMBL-EBI

susheel.varma@hdruk.ac.uk, see <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/access-to-health-data/trusted-research-environments/> :

- information is power, and human info is power over human: sensitive data is anything that needs to be protected; let's have a holistic view of health
- Sensitive data is not only personal (GDPR), but also environmental, commercial sensitive, and other...
- **Sensitive data needs to be 'shared' in a transparent open manner**
- each jurisdiction has own approach: it is thus a governance hurdle to access data
- TRE: a trusted research environment: makes research safer where data is secure, minimised, ...
 - several layers: interop etc layer, governance layer, ...
 - federated TRE user journey : FOREST: Federated, Open, & Resilient Ecosystem of Secure TREs; Federation Capacity Maturity Model
 - the biggest problem: data governance structure; each type of research implies a specific governance; there is no one stop shop: compare this to the FEGA which achieves this at the one level of data access
 - So here we are talking about different layers, data access yes, but also governance, analytics, ...
 - principles: FAIR, SAFE, CARE, TRUST
 - conclusion: cannot only be solved at technology level, but at all levels
- update from co-chairs:
 - Result: a review of vocabulary, to share a common understanding
 - highlight regional and disciplinary differences
 - Explore vocabulary from four resources:
 - 1. The GDPR Definitions
 - 2. An Australian resource titled "Sensitive Information: A specific subset of Personal Information under the Privacy Act 1988"
 - 3. The CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary
 - 4. And the "Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers Part 1: Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data used for Research Purposes"
 - A collaborative data classification activity sensitive vs non-sensitive data
- Topics of discussion
 - at what point does personal data become sensitive: of course, it is more of a spectrum;
 - The issue of pushing data management upstream, long before data access
 - Not only data sensitivity, but data quality is also critical
 - Note: GDPR & Australia: there are conversations in Australia that are questioning the old/incumbent way of thinking (i.e. de-identification, risk to the individual etc). and looking at WHO human rights - balancing individual risk vs societal benefit/risk (and doing away with the concept of de-identification/anonymisation) ; see

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/sharing-linked-data-for-health-research/7638DA9CD3F640EADD3655BCA8728214#fndtn-information>

IG Early Career and Engagement IG: *Early Careers' engagement: supporting data conversations and capacity building*

Reported by Fotis Psomopoulos ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~10 participants

The session was rather under-attended (compared to previous plenaries) - possibly due to the fact that it was purely virtual during a Plenary that had a lot of F2F sessions. The only relevant point that came up during the discussion was the potential of the ECE IG to investigate any alignment to EOSC and training (there was a participant that is active in the Skills4EOSC project).

RDA Breakout 3

[IG Vocabulary Services IG: What is going on in VSSIG?](#)

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~13 participants

The aim of this session was to present and discuss the ongoing activities of the Vocabulary Services IG (VSSIG) and its related Working Groups and Task groups.

The VSSIG has organised regular plenary sessions since the RDA 14th Plenary focusing on moving towards FAIR semantics. The IG can host informal focused discussion groups or propose formal RDA Working Groups working towards deliverables with an 18 month life cycle. The vision is to harmonise semantic web technology practices through knowledge exchange and the mission is to form an expert network where knowledge exchange can support the development of recommendations for applying the FAIR principles to vocabularies, ontologies, etc (i.e., [semantic artefacts](#)).

I-ADOPT recommendations: The [RDA I-ADOPT WG](#) has been working towards Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies and was initiated to address some of the Interoperability aspects of the FAIR data principles by enabling interoperability between existing terminologies and promoting the use of FAIR and machine-readable vocabularies. The [I-ADOPT WG outputs and recommendations](#) contains a framework for how to describe variables in a way that is both systematic and comparable to other descriptions. The work was mainly inspired by the Complex Property Model (CPM) and Scientific Variable Ontology (SVO) and I-ADOPT framework and its Observable Properties Extension provides a structure for decomposing a description of an observation into parts that can be mapped controlled terminologies and concepts that enable mappings and comparisons across datasets. The recommendations for descriptions of variables include that descriptions should be human and machine-readable, explicit and sufficient; use FAIR semantic artefacts and linked data technologies; and use the [I-ADOPT ontology](#) and [I-ADOPT aligned terminologies](#). There is also a [step-by-step guide](#) and [examples of implementations](#). I-ADOPT will be applied to infectious diseases with support from GO-FAIR at a future workshop.

Minimum metadata for semantic artefacts: Overview of work within FAIRSFair in collaboration with VSSIG to support the use of vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles and more specifically identifying a minimum set of metadata for semantic artefacts—setting a minimum threshold for what can be considered to be FAIR. Used the [MOD metadata vocabulary for ontology description and publication](#)—based on an analysis of descriptions of 800+ ontologies and 13 portals such as BioPortal, MMI, LOV, OBO Foundry—as a starting point. In process of developing MOD2.0 as an extension of DCAT for Semantic Artefact and their catalogues that will include a minimum set of required metadata. There is also ongoing work to build tooling, such as validators, catalogues, and knowledge graphs around this in FAIRSFair and the upcoming FAIR-IMPACT projects.

FAIR Semantics WG: The [FAIR Semantics recommendations](#) were developed in the FAIRsFAIR project in collaboration with the VSSIG and is currently in its third version (Feb 2022) with 17 generic recommendations and 12 best practices. An RDA Working Group could build on and refine this work with practical solutions for implementation and convergence of community driven best practices. Topics for the WG could include PID:s, metadata, tooling and governance for FAIR Semantic artefacts. Brainstorming and writing for a WG charter starting in September with aim of submitting to RDA in December 2022/January 2023.

Next steps for VSSIG: Actively seeking new co-chairs, bi-monthly calls, encouraging proposals of use cases or issues to solve, there are still several obstacles to wide-spread use of semantic artefacts that need to be addressed.

[IG Data Discovery Paradigms IG: Searching for connections: Data search, web search and literature search](#)

Reported by Fotis Psomopoulos ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~40 participants

After an overview of the general scope of the IG and the timeline so far, there were four flash presentations of invited speakers on the topic of data search studies:

1. Web Search and Literature Search During Data Discovery (Brigitte Mathiak)
2. A User Model for User-Adaptive Searching in Data Portals (Tim Suber)
3. User studies on eliciting data discovery context (Mingfang Wu)
4. Levelling up data discovery at a UK domain repository: How the UK's CEDA Archive uses a range of tools to aid users discover what they need... and the gaps that still remain. (Graham Parton)

The overarching theme, i.e. how to better make connections between the data (as provided by repositories) and the actual users by enabling better search. There were a few key insights that were highlighted by the four speakers, that may have a direct applicability to Data Repositories:

- **Monitoring tools** can be the most important step you can take -> insights into content errors and accessibility issues. Also recommend placing Names into page header elements
- Also compared queries coming in from search tools and queries recording on systems to see what **keywords (not icons)** ought to be used; use commonly used acronyms, not just names (i.e. use terms users will default to).
- **Applying ML** to learn from user behaviour related to information retrieval and recommendations systems
- Using **the right tool for the right job**:
 - Search log analysis: provide aggregated view of what users did

- Online surveys: provide way to learn more about users' backgrounds, search experiences with portal, with other tools
- Interviews: provide way to learn more in-depth information about users
- Data supplies are increasing in the data center; how to find this data is challenging for users. Solution: aim at the triangle of content, connections, and relevancy

Ultimately, the session wrapped up with a discussion around the main topic statement: *How can we enhance data discovery through the connection/integration of multiple resources, e.g. web search, literature search, data repository search, and what would be the corresponding best practices / recommendations that could be offered to repositories, aiming for user studies.* The goal here was to start a new effort towards some best practices and recommendations that would be capturing this topic.

The actual video of the session (link to be added here), may be useful to review by interested parties on the above topics.

[BoF - Electronic Laboratory Notebooks | Challenges and steps to solutions](#)

Reported by Paulette Lieby ([Collaborative notes](#))

- The problem: lack of interoperability between ELNS: lack of interface, APIs, etc... closed commercial tools, lack of integration
 - Q: Are there tools widely accepted today and open source?
- Lack of overarching ELN architecture vision within a research lab
 - It might be necessary before defining core elements of an ELN to define if the ELN is a chronological log-book, a database or a workflow system.
- facing technical problems and social problems
 - problem: diversity of requirements; no well-defined interfaces for ELNs; records in ELNs not secure, tamper-proof: so security issues
 - there is also a vast diversity of ideas and concepts what a ELN is supposed to be
 - And a big resistance to share ELNs
 - The question is whether and how to integrate the ELN with other institutional RDM resources, e.g. data storage, data management plans. Do we view the ELN as a point tool or a core infrastructure component?
- Finally, this
<https://github.com/TheELNConsortium/TheELNFileFormat/blob/master/SPECIFICATION.md> was mentioned often
 - One comment in this regard: it is a one-man show, so the question is of its sustainability, robustness,: to follow up on

RDA Breakout 4

IG Life Science Data Infrastructures IG: *Life Science Data worldwide*

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström and Paulette Lieby ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~10 participants

The aim of this session was to establish and announce the re-birth of the ELIXIR Bridging Force IG into the Life Science Data Infrastructure IG.

The session was introduced with a recap of what an interest group in RDA is and of the new charter for the Life Science Data Infrastructure IG. An IG is a long-term initiative, can produce deliverables such as surveys & reports, potentially serve as a platform for forming RDA WG:s, support communication and collaboration across RDA groups, and bridging to and bringing in communities outside of the RDA. This IG serves as a bridge between life sciences data infrastructures across the world and relevant RDA groups to address the needs for sustainable solutions for secure and easy access to highly complex data.

Participants & data infrastructures?

Top challenges?

Topics to discuss?

Balancing bottom up versus innovation

How to support common analyses across global infrastructures

Usefulness of collecting use cases based on real-world scenarios to support providers and adopters of data infrastructure services

How this group can compliment and build on existing frameworks, expanding federal open science, supporting or providing use-case resources and tools easing pain points for many early career researchers on the learning curve.

I'm mainly here to stay abreast of developments in life sciences data access, interoperability, reuse and preservation.

Based on the prior question, interoperability. What are the few capabilities that we can implement, or standards we can adopt for interoperability

[H3ABioNet](#) is a Pan African Bioinformatics Network for the Human Heredity and Health in Africa (H3Africa) consortium and beyond—including 38 partners in 17 countries with 200+ members. Developing bioinformatics skills, infrastructure and tools. Many international collaborations are tied to the major activities Bioinformatics training, Data standards and harmonisation, Data infrastructure for analysis, and Data storage and submission.

[ELIXIR](#) is a Europe-wide federated infrastructure that streamlines the storage discovery, access and exchange and analysis of life science data—including [22 national nodes & the ELIXIR hub](#) with 700+ members from over 220+ research institutes. International collaborations at many levels ranging from [ELIXIR's international strategy](#) and [EU projects](#) to [platforms](#), [communities](#), and [focus groups](#) (including a focus group on RDA activities). The vast majority of [ELIXIR services](#) are available free of charge and accessible globally by anyone interested.

The [Office of Data Science Strategy at the US National Institute of Health \(NIH\)](#) leads NIH-wide initiatives to maximise the value of the data generated through NIH-funded efforts—including 27 NIH institutes and centres across the US with their own capabilities, missions and priorities. Aim to develop interconnected data resources, policy and guidelines, useful tools and resources and a strong workforce. Some impactful examples of collaborations with the RDA include the COVID-19 IG, the Metadata Standards Catalogue WG and the FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG.

The [Office of Science at the US Department of Energy \(DOE\)](#) funds basic research in the US and relevant infrastructure programs for this group include the [Joint Genome Institute \(JGI\)](#), the [DOE Systems Biology Knowledgebase \(KBase\)](#), and the [National Microbiome Data Collaborative \(NMDC\)](#). JGI produces samples and sequences and provides access to data for reuse, it develops reusable workflows and tools to support large scale data stewardship—such as JAMO (JGI Archive and Metadata Organiser). NMDC provides a gateway to FAIR multi-omics microbiome data focusing on standards training and how to plan for good data management. KBase is a free, open-source collaborative

knowledge creation, discovery and dissemination platform designed for both biologists and bioinformaticians to support the full research lifecycle. Collaborations tied to the different programs, relatively new to RDA, examples of RDA groups include Data Usage Metrics WG and Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG.

[Australian BioCommons](#) support life science research communities with community scale digital infrastructure including computational services, training and support. Engage through various topic areas and facilitate interactions with computational and bioinformatics infrastructure providers. Many collaborations around data infrastructure for analysis, compute, human genomics data, biodiversity data, AAI, and bioinformatics training. Just now on the verge of starting engagement with the RDA.

How does this group fit into the RDA?

- There are several examples of Interest Groups and Working Groups where we could contribute with our experiences and perspectives to make the outputs better suited to the life science community and we could also benefit from adopting or collaborating on developing solutions.
- The RDA Activities Focus Group in ELIXIR promotes a travel grant for attending to RDA Plenaries, invites attendees to connect and collaborate on a report from each Plenary, and is preparing a survey on RDA engagement among its members.
- In the past the ELIXIR Bridging Force has co-organised sessions with other IGs and that might be something to consider for the future as well.
- In the context of this IG, it could be interesting to establish an overview of which groups we are represented in, what would be interesting topics to pool knowledge around, share experience of or opportunities for adopting RDA outputs, and maintain a curated list of resources to support researchers.

FAIR for infrastructure could be a topic to bring up for discussion in the context of this IG. A call for input on future work and modes of engagement will be distributed to participants and members of the IG.

[WG FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG: FAIR4RS - FAIR principles for research software outcomes and governance](#)

Reported by Fotis Psomopoulos ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~ 15 participants

The main purpose of the session was to present the overall work and output of the FAIR4RS WG, prior to it being closed, with the maintenance of the work being given to the Software Source Code IG. The vast majority of the participants were already involved with the FAIR4RS WG, and had experience in both using and creating software.

The main outputs presented were:

- The actual FAIR₄RS Principles, ready to adopt and use <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>
- The general [FAIR₄RS outputs page](#)
- The secondary publications and outputs available on [Zenodo](#)
- The relevant bibliography collected on [Zotero](#)

In addition to this overview, there were some interactions with the attendees, focusing around two key questions: “Do you or your organisation follow institutional or community best practices with the software source code you create?”, and “Do you or your organisation use the FAIR₄RS? Do you plan on using it?”. Based on the received feedback, there is definitely a need for Best Practices, with very few organisations currently using the FAIR Principles for Software in a systematic way (most of the approaches were rather practical, such as using GitHub/GitLab or language-specific standards). However, there was a strong interest in picking up the FAIR₄RS output, either as a potential template for smaller projects in order to test it out, or by adding them to a list of “approved”/“aspirational” guidelines to be followed.

The actual video of the session (link to be added here), may be useful to review, looking at possible connections to ELIXIR-related activities (such as OpenEBench and the Software Management Plan).

RDA Breakout 5

WG GORC International Model WG: *Global Open Research Commons IG update and GORC International Model WG: Reflections and Document Development*

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~17 participants

The aim of this session was to highlight the purpose and progress of activities in the [Global Open Research Commons \(GORC\) IG](#) and to invite contributions to a document where the [GORC International Models WG](#) will collect and curate a set of attributes that will allow Commons developers to compare features across science clouds and commons.

The session was opened with an overview of some of the [definitions introduced in the IG](#). A research commons is a trusted ecosystem that provides seamless access to high quality interoperable research outputs and services. Commons initiatives can be categorised by type of e-infrastructure, geographic region, scientific domain etc. And a Commons includes a spectrum of elements ranging from IT, research objects and standards to governance, engagement and sustainability as illustrated by the following diagram:

Some of the activities described in this session have also been proposed as topics for future RDA group activities. The *Data Commons Principles and implementation* BoF session proposes to address high level aspirational goals; map high level principles to best practice and implementation; and community building. The *Research Data Spaces Taxonomy* BoF session proposes expanding from efforts in EU context; focus on taxonomy/defs of data spaces; including non-national level infra. Speakers include NIH, one of the inspirations from the Global Open Research Commons model; other domain data commons from environmental sciences, genomics, cancer; and the projects FAIRCore4EOSC/FAIR-MPACT that will be working in this space.

[European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) will become the European data space for the research sector and it's one of 13 data spaces just starting to develop in the EU data strategy, other sectors including health, mobility, agriculture, tourism etc. EOSC is envisioned as an ecosystem with common standards to link existing infrastructures as a federation (e.g., not centralisation) with 4 main strands: 1) policies and incentives for open science, 2) data management compatible with the FAIR data principles, 3) federated access to data and services, and 4) community engagement (the wide range of stakeholders is a big challenge). This means bringing together existing federations that support research; to include national and institutional structures into the portfolio; and also bring in more specific Research Infrastructures (RIs) tailored to specific needs. Ultimately providing common discovery and access mechanisms without putting everything in one repository as well as promoting interoperability across RI services and links across research outputs, publications, researchers etc.

There is currently a catalogue of services that will develop into something that will enable integration of the services into something like working environments. Direction provided by EOSC Association, the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and 13 task forces working to progress different areas of EOSC. RDA can help provide global consensus and promote global solutions.

[Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\)](#) is a national research infrastructure in Australia with a purpose is to provide Australian researchers with competitive advantage through data by driving excellence in the creation, analysis and retention of data assets. ARDC has a services catalogue pulling together resources provided by others and where ARDC fills gaps that are identified. Currently covering a research cloud, data discovery (harvesting metadata from other institutions), persistent identifiers, vocabularies, investment in currently 26 Virtual Research Environments (VREs), communities of practices, and support/hub of expertise. One national commons, building thematic subcommons such as for humanities & social science, health & medicine, ecology & agriculture etc. VREs build on central services such as virtual desktop services provided by ARDC. Data discovery based on ISO 2164 (with OAI-PMH) but moving towards Schema.org. Issued ORCID:s and DOI:s. Global engagement through RDA, CODATA GOSC Task Forces, Research Software Alliance (RSA). Promotes CoreTrustSeal for repositories. No formal rules of participation, governance arrangements vary, institutions required to sign agreements to use resources, work/advocacy at national policy level/incentives.

The [GORC International Models WG](#) has confirmed participation from *pan-national commons*—such as EOSC, Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC)—, *domain commons*—such as International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA), Canadian Consortium for Arctic Data Interoperability (CCADI)—, and a range of national commons—such as AARDC (Australia), CSTCloud (China), KISTI (South Korea), NII Research Data Cloud (Japan), The Alliance (Canada) etc. A range of potential participants have been identified, including domain commons such as GBIF, GA4GH, US Cancer Research Data Commons. Currently working on a shared document with key takeaways and lessons learned from case studies and identifying the high-level functions that are provided across pan-national, national and domain commons. Currently running a speaker series to present different science clouds and Commons initiatives, to test the [definitions introduced in the IG](#) and to develop a set of attributes that will allow developers to compare features. The group is open to new members and a presentation of ELIXIR would be appreciated in this context.

[IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG: A Fabric for FAIR Digital Objects](#)

Reported by Paulette Lieby ([collaborative notes](#)) ~ 24 participants

- Components and services in an FDO framework: the point/issue is machine readability:
 - machines handling in face of a variety of data types, formats, ...
 - how to make type information machine readable? encoded in PIDs? types?
 - xml: a hierarchy of information pairs
 - Or a universal pattern: key structure described in a registry;
 - Therefore, a need for a an interoperable type registry landscape: registries describe structures for value spaces
 - Requires a (minimal) data model for type definition, type attributes and profile describing them
 - an internet of data
 - An abstraction of a DO architecture/layer
- An example: electric butterflies (Dimitris Koureas)
 - a large scale implementation: natural science collection
 - --> to lower access cost to national collections
 - replicate physical object attribute into a digital surrogate FDO: an actionable knowledge unit (readable/interpretable/actionable)
 - a meaningful and self-interpretable integrated data space
 - from a physical scientific curation to a digital scientific curation
 - way beyond digitisation of collections --> interpret and interact with digital objects
- Announcement:
 - **FDO forum, FDOs building blocks of integrated digital space**
 - **26-28 Oct 22: 1st international conference in Leiden**
 - **expecting to issue the Leiden declaration**

Joint session: [Working and Interest Group Chairs CG](#), [WG RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange \(Scholix\) WG](#), [WG FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#), [IG Software Source Code IG: Supporting FAIR in software](#)

Reported by Marek Suchánek ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~ 26 participants

The session consisted of three interesting presentations on approaches supporting FAIR in software (and even beyond FAIR) in different ecosystems/environments. First, Morane Gruenpeter (Inria) presented [Software Heritage \(SWH\)](#) as a non-profit organisation with the goal to collect, preserve and share all software source code. SWH uses its own persistent identifiers [SWHID](#). It was also emphasised that software can be the result of research and thus needs reproducibility and visibility. There is collaboration between SWH and [HAL open archive](#) (e.g. in terms of using SWHID). SWH refers to software using VCS (e.g. git or svn), metadata are then indexed automatically and then moderated by the digital archivist team. A useful but not mandatory is codemeta.json file (see <https://codemeta.github.io/>). Another possibility/perspective is provided by the [CITATION.cff](#) file that can be also indexed. As a final message was a statement that FAIR is not enough and there is much more in software towards being also open-source and reproducible.

The second presentation by Tom Honeyman from [ARDC](#) was about a Research Software Agenda for Australia. He briefly explained what is the current status and plans for the future in terms of FAIR software support in Australia. The main resource mentioned is the National Agenda for Research Software (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378082>). The vision is that "research software is recognised as a first-class output of research".

The third presenter, Rachel Lammey ([Crossref](#)), talked about [Scholix](#) and Software. Scholix is a framework for scholarly link exchange; basically it is a set of guidelines on how to expose and consume links that is supported by "hubs" (e.g. [DataCite](#) or [Crossref](#)). The focus of Scholix is on linking articles and datasets. However, links to software are already being established as well. There is work being done on extending the Scholix schema to adapt to "Software" resources and various links between them and also resources of other types. Updates in the schema will be validated with different stakeholder groups and RDA will be asked to endorse the updated schema.

[WG Data Repository Attributes WG: Data Repository Attributes Working Group \(DRAWG\) Launch Meeting](#)

Reported by Allyson Lister

At the RDA19 Plenary (also part of IDW2022), I was the RDA Data Repository Attributes WG co-chair and session co-lead ([notes](#), my [slides](#)). Following the endorsement and kick off of this WG since P18,

this session confirmed the direction and deliverables of the group. Group discussion and interactive polling was used to capture input from attendees about key features of repositories to add to the current list and some initial ranking to help with prioritisation. [Summary of outcomes](#).

RDA Breakout 6

WG CURE-FAIR WG: [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~9+ participants

The aim of this session was to present the *10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research* output produced by the CURE-FAIR WG and to highlight opportunities for adoption and future work related to reproducible research.

Brief overview of CURE-FAIR: Aims to establish guidelines and identify best practices for curating bundles of data and code to support computational reproducibility and sharing according to the FAIR data principles. Initiated as a BoF at RDA 14th Plenary transitioning to endorsed RDA working group and organised work 15th–16th, community input and review at 17th–18th, and today presenting the RDA recommendation outlining guidelines for CURE-FAIR practices in publishing and archiving computationally reproducible studies. The object of curation is a bundle of all the data, code, documentation and other files that would be necessary to independently understand and repeat the analysis workflow from processing and transformation to producing the results—this is called a *research compendium* or a *reproducible file bundle*. The WG produced supporting outputs including a report on [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#), an [annotated bibliography related to CURE-FAIR practices](#), and currently conducting [a survey to collect stories from CURE-FAIR practitioners](#).

[RDA Recommendation 10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#): Standards-based guidelines, currently developed with a focus on social science research that relies on quantitative data, and aimed towards curators, researchers, publishers and other stakeholders in creating, using, sharing, publishing or preserving reproducible research. Each of the 10 things describes an issue followed by three actionable sections to *Get started*, *Learn more* and *Go deeper*. The major questions being addressed are roughly: Does the research compendium contain all files necessary? Is it sufficiently documented? What are the terms and conditions for (re)use? Is it machine-actionable? How will it be maintained long-term? The 10 things are summarised in the table below:

1. Completeness The research compendium contains all of the objects needed to reproduce a predefined outcome.	6. Access It is clear who can use what, how, and under what conditions, with "open" being preferred.
2. Organisation It is easy to understand and keep track of the various objects in the research compendium.	7. Provenance The origin of the components of the compendium and how each has changed over time is evident.

3. Economy Fewer objects in the compendium mean fewer things that can break and less ongoing maintenance.	8. Metadata Information about the compendium and its components is embedded in a standardised schematic code.
4. Transparency The full context necessary to understand the research process is available.	9. Automation As much as possible, the computational workflow is script-based to allow re-execution with minimal actions.
5. Documentation The process and reasoning required to reproduce a scientific claim are readily available and understandable.	10. Review A series of managed activities are in place to ensure continued access to and functionality of the compendium.

Adopter stories: The Odum Institute at University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill and Cornell Center for Social Sciences at Cornell University were highlighted as examples of adopters where they've been used as part of standards-based practice, in training programs, and when describing services that they offer to researchers. The 10 Things can be a framework for aspects to consider when building or looking to improve local practices for preparing research compendia for publishing and preservation. They can also be referred to as explanations and motivations for practices / requirements that support reproducibility.

Next steps: The WG is transitioning to maintenance mode. Future work could continue in new or existing RDA groups focusing on reproducibility, research engagement and/or curation. Related RDA groups include Reproducibility IG, which seems to be dormant but could possibly be revived, and the Reproducible Health Data Services IG, which seems to be active today.

[BoF - Is FAIR FAIR? A discussion of the overlaps in the FAIR principles of data management and AI-Readiness](#)

Reported by Fotis Psomopoulos ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~ 12 participants

The main goal of this session was to review the topic of AI-Readiness, looking at the various existing efforts both within RDA and beyond. AI-readiness can be defined as, "...taking steps to collect data around relevant systems, equipment, and procedures; and storing and curating that data in a way that makes it easily accessible to others for use in future AI applications." (US DoD - AI in Defense). In this context, and although there are a few efforts under RDA that tackle FAIR Machine Learning and FAIR Digital Objects, there are no current RDA groups explicitly addressing AI-Readiness.

The session itself comprised of three main talks:

- Outline of the FAIR4ML effort (new IG forming) - [Slides](#)
- Overview of the FDO Activities in RDA - [Slides](#)
- Review of AI Readiness looking at machine-actionable ways to transfer data from repositories to analysis - [link to roadmap](#)

The overall feedback from the participants was that there is definitely an interest in identifying and connecting FAIR to Machine Learning. In this context, it may be useful to engage (in particular to the new FAIR4ML IG), looking at various standards and activities that are currently in progress under ELIXIR.

The actual video of the session (link to be added here), may be useful to review,

[WG FAIR Data Maturity Model WG: The FAIR Data Maturity Model in practice: learning from adoption](#)

Reported by Paulette Lieby ([Collaborative notes](#)) 15-19 participants

- the FDMM WG: the issues
 - FAIR principles are not strict but subject to a wide range of interpretations
 - There are different evaluation/assessment frameworks
 - And FDMM is not yet another evaluation method
- > 1st FDMM published (established with the help of PWC), now in maintenance mode
- perspectives on adoption and implementation: a EOSC FAIR metrics and Data Quality Task Force has been setup (lead Mark Wilkinson):
 - - along 3 axis of work: FAIR metrics / FAIR evaluation / FAIR governance
 - - there are 13 FAIR evaluation platforms! (see [fairassist.org](#)), each with different outcomes
 - - so we need harmonisation —through EOSC + GOFAIR hackathons
 - - there already are a few answers:
 - --> define unambiguous links, pure web, only link relations
 - --> define evaluation benchmarks
 - --> hackathon: FAIRness levels connected to FAIRsharing (see status change in FAIRsharing)
 - --> a white paper is in progress : will be submitted for a review
 - A difficult issue: provenance
 - Where does it sit? With the data's collector? originator?
- Adoption of FDMM
 - This typically needs organisational change (a 'FAIR roadmap') to even be in a position to adopt RDA FDMM: see

Just Published: Lightsom, F.L., Hutchison, V.B., Bishop, B., Debrewer, L.M., Govoni, D.L., Latysh, N., and Stall, S., 2022, Opportunities to improve alignment with the FAIR Principles for U.S. Geological Survey data: U.S. Geological Survey Open-File Report 2022–1043, 23 p., <https://doi.org/10.3133/ofr20221043> (proposé par Shelley Stall)

- example from Markus Kubin (HMC): different levels, eg data level (I & R), repository level (F & A), instrument assessments (I & R); see <https://idw2022.events.whova.com/Artifact/55942>
- Discussion around governance & RDA recommendations governance; somme comments:
 - Authority is with the money. Responsibility is with the scientific community, - and lets not forget scholarly societies, the heart of any academic community: *centrality of the research community*
 - best support out of domain repositories
 - Also funder responsibility
- Discussion: Tension between disciplinary vs interdisciplinarity / **FAIR for whom?**; a few comments from participants (direct quotes in italics)
 - **keep in mind all dimensions of data reuse** (eg biodiversity–ie, beyond the confines of one's community ...)
 - *maybe the first aim is to be shareable within the community?*
 - *I'm not sure we can go for the approach of saying "this is FAIR for this community" when FAIR expects data to be shared across communities?*
 - *In this space of thinking about the borders of FAIR, I would offer the practice of designing for accessibility: when you design for the edges, you will satisfy everything in between them.*
 - *Always, for each FDMM principle, the question could be "in my case, what is efficient, sufficient and appropriate?"*
 - e.g., DOI applicable to one project, one experiment of the project, one dataset in an experiment (for instance), one file of the dataset, one record of the file etc... : issue of granularity so that data can be reused without being knowledgeable about all the ways data can be described
 - There are several MM; depends on object type under consideration (ontologies, images, etc...); provenance aspect: hardly resolved today, question of sustainability - the test to be 'really' reusable is an excellent one -

RDA Breakout 7

WG Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG: Discipline-specific Guidance for Data WG Discipline-specific Guidance for DMPs

Reported by Paulette Lieby ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~10 participants

- objectives : increasing value of DMPs to researchers
- results of online survey:
 - 358 respondents
 - from most of the world, all disciplines, all data types
 - data reuse, quality control, metadata, supporting documentation, ELSI issues, use of RDM guidelines
- Discussion
 - Mention of RMDkit
 - how to develop a guidance, structure, format?
 - visual and/or text, content is not the topic of discussion today,
 - how disciplines are spreading/disseminating information; how they are working with RDM
 - who is your audience: type of medium, ie cultural viewpoint
 - success stories, demonstrating RDM benefits
 - FAQ
 - working with people within the discipline
- Where to share the guidance?
 - looking for multipliers (eg AU data commons)
- maintain/sustain the guidance
 - a difficult question: want something stable but still reacting to latest developments
 - community involvement, industry peak bodies, via github; but this may not be appropriate for all disciplines; example of RDMkit
 - Catathon
 - how much to specialise template wrt different discipline
- institutional surveys around needs/demands
 - top is DMP, because in most places it is now compulsory

SciDataCon Sessions

Supporting Research Transparency, Accountability, and Reproducibility: Lessons from the Trenches (317)

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([session description](#))

The aim of this session was to explore how different groups have been working to ensure that research results are computationally reproducible by taking steps to prevent digital obsolescence of the supporting data and code.

The session was introduced with a brief overview of the topic and [a report on Reproducibility and Replicability in Science](#). Together with rigour, transparency and independent verifications reproducibility can be viewed as cornerstones of the scientific method. Computational reproducibility (reproducibility) is being able to get consistent results using the same data, computational steps, methods, code, and conditions. Having reproducibility does not imply that results are correct and not having reproducibility does not directly imply that results are wrong. Providing sufficient information about the computational methods and data products that support the results and access to relevant data and code help to ensure reproducibility. Obsolescence of the digital files supporting the results have been identified as a key obstacle to long-term reproducibility. Solutions include trusted repositories that can store, curate and enable access to the relevant materials.

The [Cornell Center for Social Sciences \(CCSS\) Reproducibility of Results Service \(R Squared\)](#): A service to affiliated researchers that offers verification of computational reproducibility before submitting a paper for publication. The staff will rerun the analysis and check that the results are the same. In the process they will review the code and instructions provided, verify that the code runs without errors, and assist with improving and packaging the necessary files in a way that is suitable for publication in a CTS certified institutional repository (CCSS Data and Reproduction Archive).

[The Curating for Reproducibility \(CURE\) Consortium](#): A forum to collaborate on how to support curation of research data and review of code and associated digital scholarly objects for the purpose of facilitating the digital preservation of the evidence base necessary for future understanding, evaluation, and reproducibility of scientific claims. Agreed on four guiding principles *Transparency + Access + Trust*: underlying research objects are made available; *Usability*: independently understandable and usable; *Independence*: runnable on independent compute platforms by third parties; and *Prepublication*: verify reproducibility before publishing. And work to share practices, promote data quality review, and establish standards.

Current member organisations include CCSS (above), University of North Carolina (UNC) Odum Institute for Research in Social Science, and Yale Institution for Social and Policy Studies (ISPS). In contrast to CCSS the Odum Institute provides a similar service but by partnering with journal editors,

where authors of accepted papers are then required to submit the supporting materials for verification of computational reproducibility before they are published. Yale ISPS has established a workflow that all of the institution's researchers should follow to ensure computational reproducibility of the research that they conduct.

[Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\)](#): A national research infrastructure facility to provide Australian researchers with a competitive advantage through data by driving excellence in the creation, analysis and retention of high quality data assets. The [ARDC's National Agenda for Research Software](#) and the corresponding program of work is relevant in this context since it aims to promote recognition of research software as an output closer in line with recognition of a published paper by driving the establishment of a support system for visibility, reuse and sustainability.

The [PARSEC](#) project's workshop [Round Table Brazil](#): A 2h workshop on workflow management and reproducibility conducted in April 2021 with PARSEC project members and participants from across the world. Discussions on their experiences in workflow management and reproducibility, what challenges they have faced, and how they have overcome them.

Other examples mentioned in the session description included the [CASCaD](#) reproducibility certification service and the [Knowledge Exchange](#) partnership (six key national organisations in Europe) and their recent report [The Art of Publishing Reproducible Research Outputs: Supporting emerging practices through cultural and technological innovation](#).

The session concluded with an extensive panel discussion on challenges. Some of the challenges mentioned included disparate rates of culture change / drivers towards open science; variation in time and effort required to validate/curate articles for reproducibility; promoting citations and publishing of software/code in addition to data; as well as the utility of computational notebooks and the importance of different types of repositories for software, data and code. Work towards finding solutions is going to continue for a long time and is going to slow us down but the opportunity is to do science better.

Where are the vocabularies that make environmental datasets FAIR? (428)

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Session description](#))

The aim of this session was to identify challenges and solutions to adopting and promoting vocabularies that are controlled, standardised, and persistent (5+ years into the future) to maintain integrity of datasets in the environmental and earth sciences.

The session was opened with four presentations covering topics related to challenges and potential solutions to making vocabularies more FAIR and also more accessible. Why should research scientists worry about controlled vocabularies? Vocabularies—how do I know which ones are authoritative, which

ones are FAIR and which ones will still be available online in 2040? Managing Community Shared Vocabularies. And experiences from developing standards, terms and definitions to support interoperability. The session concluded with a panel discussion and Q&A.

Why should research scientists worry about controlled vocabularies? Interoperability across datasets requires that data elements and values are compatible by conforming to either identical vocabularies or vocabularies that have been aligned to each other. The vocabularies themselves also need to be findable and accessible in the long-term and ideally conform with the FAIR data principles. Semantic repositories that are specialised in housing vocabularies and can support content and technical governance governance.

Today, data is often aligned with controlled vocabularies at the end of the data life cycle, before publishing or archiving. A more desirable situation would be for researchers to use vocabularies when they create the data and to describe their variables, units of measurements, instruments etc. Local names and definitions for variables can be annotated using properties that allow mappings to existing vocabularies and definitions.

Defining experiment variables using controlled vocabularies can be complex but once mapped for an experimental setup they can be reused across many studies and research projects, and ultimately resulting in efficient publishing and data management practices. Experimental variables can be described precisely and consistently using ontologies and frameworks such as [I-ADOPT](#), supporting tools such as converters (semantic brokers), connectors (semantic bridges) and dynamic mapping tools.

Criteria for selecting a vocabulary: Is the terminology FAIR? Is it supported by an active, responsive, established technical governance? Is it well maintained, documented, and connected to other terminologies? Has it got rules of governance? Does it have a large user base? Is it recommended by many?

Researchers and vocabulary experts should engage in developing and promoting FAIR vocabularies to realise the benefits of FAIR and machine-actionable data. The researchers know the details of what their data represent and what information to include to enhance the interoperability, re-usability and traceability. Start early at the planning, collection, processing stages.

Vocabularies—how do I know which ones are authoritative, which ones are FAIR and which ones will still be available online in 2040? Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) has been conducting two community activities that aimed to help researchers determine what vocabularies to choose: 1) Identifying semantic resources (such as vocabularies and ontologies) and 2) providing guidance to the vocabularies by annotations indicating where they are used and for what purpose.

RDA ESES-IG developed [a list of vocabulary, ontology and semantic repositories/services](#) that are available online for Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences. To be useful the list should be maintained and the resources should be searchable and annotated with information about their scientific applications, governance.

[Research Vocabularies Australia](#) is a registry service that helps researchers find, access, and reuse vocabularies for research. As more vocabularies have been published it's become difficult for

researchers to determine which term from what vocabulary to use. Currently working towards being able to provide an interface for providing domain/community guidance based on surveying facilities and exploring a model for annotating vocabularies.

Managing Community Shared Vocabularies: [The CUAHSI Hydrologic Information System](#) was developed for discovering, accessing, and publishing time-series and sensor data. Since there was no standard information model or accepted vocabulary for sharing hydrologic time series data at the time, the [WaterML XML exchange format](#) and the [Observations Data Model \(ODM2\)](#) were developed to describe many observational data types with metadata about the variables, units and contextual information about the sample collection, splitting, processing, analysis and results.

Initially maintained a concept tree / mapping to support grouping similar terms in the data discovery services but eventually transitioned to exposing a controlled vocabulary service to propose new / updated terms—see [Managing a community shared vocabulary for hydrologic observations \(Horsburgh et al. 2014\)](#).

Vocabularies have most meaning within a domain information model (e.g. ODM2, WaterML), consensus on a model and related vocabularies requires a community of users, governance and supporting vocabulary management infrastructure. Vocabularies can enhance greater consistency but mappings will still be required and getting people to use them to describe their data is hard. Maintaining vocabulary and associated systems requires long-term commitment (a community service organising is probably the best place).

Bushfire Fuels in Australia: AFAC, the National Council for fire and emergency services, have initiated work on developing standards, terms and definitions that would bring together and harmonise data on fuel types from different jurisdictions across Australia. An example highlighted was how 430 fuel-types were translated into 8 high-level behavioural models that would be used in predictive modelling to support interventions and in research. The initiative was organised with a central group responsible for developing the guideline with input from stakeholders in a working group and wider network of users. The guideline would define standard terms, data definitions, and standardised collection methods to avoid subjective measurements.

Read the papers supporting the session:

<https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/428/>

Scientific Vocabularies: needs, status, validity, governance and sustainability (461)

Reported by Allyson Lister (presenting) and Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Collaborative notes](#)) ~42 participants

The aim of this session was to address governance concerns related to scientific vocabularies and how to encode information related to governance as metadata to support vocabulary assessment and selection.

Allyson was a session speaker for [Scientific Vocabularies: needs, status, validity, governance and sustainability](#). (Her [slides](#)). She described the role of ontologies and their governance within FAIRsharing and the Community Curation Programme, which is part of the EOSC Future / RDA Domain Ambassador programme of which she is a part.

Governance concerns

Vocabulary governance – 6 key concerns: Following the [Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR](#) publication [a workshop focusing on FAIR vocabularies for interoperability in cross-domain research](#) was arranged. The first of the ten rules is concerned with governance and custodian arrangements and leading up to the workshop a draft set of rules for governance and maintenance was proposed and rejected in favour of a set of broader concerns. It would be difficult to identify a set of rules that could apply equally as it evolves from genesis of a new vocabulary used in a research group to a stable vocabulary that is globally relied on. The following six key concerns should be addressed with suitable solutions: 1) Scope and context; 2) Stakeholders; 3) Content management; 4) Revision and change requests; 5) Implementation and communication of changes; 6) Persistence and sustainability. Each concern was described in more detail and they are summarised in the [abstract for the presentation](#).

A Working Group focusing on FAIR Vocabularies for population research: The [FAIR Vocabularies Working Group](#) is a joint working group between CODATA and IUSSP to make demographic data more interoperable by publishing FAIR vocabularies—working on implementing the ten rules for making a vocabulary FAIR across a selection of case studies and technologies. Use cases for controlled vocabularies include *data discovery*, *data merging*, and *data harmonisation*. And in this context vocabularies are conceptualised in four levels 1) Concept; 2) Measure / Variable; 3) Code list / Value domain; 4) Code mapping / Crosswalk. Macro-data are aggregates for nations, regions or other units—adopt shared vocabularies, promote standards for exchange and long-lived/governed standards. Micro-data are about individual people, businesses or events—project specific vocabularies with some reuse, few incentives to share vocabularies, data repositories promote standards (e.g. CESSDA). Demopaedia, ELSST, SDMX and IPUMS are examples of resources for controlled vocabularies with various degrees of vocabulary levels and FAIRness. [ELSST \(European Language Social Science Thesaurus\)](#) was reported to be FAIR and contains concepts and variables whereas [IPUMS \(Integrated Public Use Microdata Series\)](#) also contained code mappings to harmonised variables but was not FAIR. Other fields define terms in ways that are contrary to population studies (e.g. fertility) so it's important to not fall behind and make the relevant vocabularies available.

[The evolution of a geoscience standard](#) (Parsons, 2022): The 35-year evolution of the [Global Change Master Directory \(GCMD\) Keywords](#) for earth science was presented as an instructive example of the development and adoption of a scientific vocabulary. Initially established as part of the Directory Interchange Format (DIF) followed by broad adoption with subsets of keywords in data portals, emerging needs for technical evolution and subsequent retooling resulting in a well maintained and broadly adopted standard with multiple formats and APIs. The vocabulary is strictly hierarchical and if the same term occurs in multiple branches each of the occurrences will have a unique identifier—this works well for legacy systems but does not fit well with modern ontology design. The need for institutional commitment and community engagement was highlighted as essential to any system strategy or design and balancing their respective objectives as the central challenge. Proposed solutions include adopting an agile approach to maintain a balance of centralised control and distributed adoption/adaptation and focusing on transparent maintenance, decision mechanisms and incentives. Future development of the vocabulary should move from the strict hierarchy towards a graph model that can represent relationships between terms and support interdisciplinary interoperability.

Governing vocabularies in astronomy: [The International Virtual Observatory Alliance \(IOVA\)](#) was created in 2002 to debate and agree on standards that enable astronomical datasets and other resources to work as a seamless whole—a Virtual Observatory (VO). The [standard for Unified Content Descriptors \(UCDs\)](#) was first published in 2005, building on [previous work to harmonise data column descriptors for a collection of about 5000 data tables](#) containing a total of about 100 000 columns with inconsistent naming conventions. A procedure for [maintenance of the list of UCDs](#) was published as a companion to UCDs according to which several revisions have been published. [The IVOA Document Standards](#) is a description of the types of documents it publishes and its processes to advance drafts to recommendations—inspired by W3C. Proposed recommendations are produced with reference implementations, then submitted as a Request for Comments (RFC) open to the IVOA community, examined by a Technical Coordination Group, and finally promoted to a recommendation by the IVOA Executive Board. The Executive Board is composed of representatives from national and regional VO initiatives and the Technical Coordination Group is composed of chairs and vice chairs from IVOA Working Groups (WG) and Interest Groups (IG). [The Semantics WG](#) manages the standard for UCDs and a recommendation on [units in the VO](#) as well as a set of RDF-based [vocabularies](#) that are maintained through [Vocabulary Enhancement Proposals \(VEPs\)](#). The [IOVA registry metadata schema](#) includes Dublin Core elements and disciplinary extensions for cross-disciplinary findability and [all IVOA documents & standards](#) are collected at their website (organised by type, WG/IG and maturity levels).

Geospatial reference data as the next step after vocabularies: Adopting semantic web technologies is often a series of small steps to increase the value provided to the organisation. Some of the first steps could include adopting vocabularies that represent concepts and simple relations that could be modelled using SKOS; followed by adding specialised properties ("SKOS+")—such as versioning, provenance, domain modelling etc—to support new use cases that add value. Adopting geospatial data

standards for useful reference datasets can be a natural next step since many organisations have geospatial information that they rely on, making lists of geospatial features is relatively easy, and encoding the information according to modern data standards is similar to vocabularies (cf. SKOS Concept and Feature in [OGC API / GeoSPARQL](#)). Continuing on the same path could include adopting standards for other types of potential reference datasets and progressing to integrated semantic web data. The [OGC LD API](#) and [Prez](#) tools were highlighted as examples of tools for presenting "SKOS+" vocabularies and geospatial reference data using a [live demo](#).

Encoding of governance information

Governance and maintenance concerns for the Australian soil domain: The aims for the Australian National Soil Information System (ANSIS) include creating FAIR semantic web vocabularies for national standards and proposing a governance process. A discussion paper was drafted to stimulate the conversation between stakeholders on governance concerns focusing on three different types of soil standards—ranging in complexity from inventory, to interlinked vocabulary, to ontology. Permission was received from the publisher of each standard and the [Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR](#) were used as a guide to assess and implement them as FAIR vocabularies. The vocabularies were annotated with metadata, the terms were assigned identifiers and were encoded in SKOS maintained under [GitHub.com/ANZSoilData](#). The vocabularies were registered in [Research Vocabularies Australia](#) with URI redirects to anzsoil.org. Backward compatibility across versions varied between vocabularies and would impact the governance, custodianship and stakeholder consultations. The [six key concerns for governance](#) (also [FAIR vocabularies workshop report](#)) were considered for the three standards, resulting in a draft proposal with a set of key questions to support the discussions.

Curation and governance of an ecosystem of research standards and databases: [FAIRsharing](#) stores descriptions of standards (including terminologies), databases and policies. Two internally developed/maintained vocabularies support discoverability and curation of relationships across resources, organisations and domains. The [subject ontology](#) is mostly manually generated and covers 436 academic disciplines from 7 public vocabularies (see [subject browser](#)). The [domain ontology](#) is mostly machine generated and covers 968 domains from 50+ public vocabularies (see [record for ISO/DIS 20691](#) & [graph](#)). Both vocabularies align with the [OBO Foundry's principles](#) and in practices with the key concerns for governance. FAIRsharing has worked with the research community to develop common sets of attributes for describing policies and databases, and is interested in developing a similar common set of attributes for terminologies (see [record for IVOA UCD](#)). Common *descriptions* of ontologies are as important in ontology governance as common metadata to use *within* those terminologies, as these descriptions can help improve findability and assessment.

Minimum metadata for FAIR Semantic artefacts: The [FAIR Semantics Recommendations](#) addresses how to build FAIR semantic artefacts (e.g. codelists, thesauri, vocabularies, ontologies etc). The FAIRsFAIR's project and the [RDA Vocabulary Services IG](#) have been working to set a threshold for what constitutes *rich metadata* in line with the FAIR principles (e.g. I2, F2, R1) and define the corresponding

minimum common metadata required. Some work had been done on metadata for ontologies—such as a [survey](#), the [metadata for Ontology Description and publication \(MOD\)](#) vocabulary, and the [AgroPortal repository](#). Work on developing [MOD 2.0](#) as a [DCAT 2 profile](#) for semantic artefacts has started, a set of 12 properties were identified as the minimum metadata for FAIR, and a proof of concept catalogue is being developed to aggregate and publish the contents of BioPortal, AgroPortal and NERC Vocabulary service as a FAIR Data Point and with a SPARQL endpoint (see [FAIRsFAIR/SemanticDCAT-AP](#)).

Static site generators for semantic web vocabulary publication: Static site generators were highlighted as a low effort & cost and robust option for publishing vocabularies for organisations that don't want to adopt more specialised systems. The output from a static site generator can be published on any web server and there are services such as GitHub Pages and Gitlab that offer both access to the tools and the web server for the output. Example [vocabulary website](#) and [source on GitHub](#)).

Wrap up: Is there anything missing from the list of governance concerns? What can we as a community do next to advance practices in addressing the governance concerns and encoding of governance information for vocabularies? What are the problems of adopting the list of governance concerns?

Practical Cross-Domain Data Sharing: Envisioning a Core Interoperability Framework (438)

Reported by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström ([Session description and supporting materials](#))

The aim of this session was to highlight some of the work that has been done in building a cross-domain interoperability layer on top of the FAIR Digital Object Framework and to suggest a path forward.

I. Overview of Requirements and Potential Candidate Standards for a Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework

The FAIR Digital Object Framework (FDOF) was highlighted as a work in progress towards a technical foundation to support FAIR data sharing—and was compared to the stack of communications protocols (TCP IP etc) that enables the Web. Its components specify FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) that provide a human and machine readable description of how a specific community (e.g., a project, a disciplinary domain, ...) conforms with FAIR as well as FAIR Data Point (FDP) repositories with FAIR

Digital Objects (FDOs).

Accessing a FIP provides a human and machine readable answer to what standards/models (metadata, vocabularies, file formats value encoding etc) are used and how to interact with the relevant registries and repositories in a community. Convergence on a set of standards that can function across communities is still important to be able to develop tools and services that link and integrate resources from other communities.

A Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) would provide a “core” set of standards/models to support common functions—such as finding, assessing, getting access, importing, understanding (semantic and provenance), using and managing FAIR data. So far, much focus has been on findability, some on interoperability and reuse but little on accessibility.

- *Findability*: Solutions for descriptive metadata derived from Dublin Core, such as Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT) and Schema.org, as well as persistent identifiers that can be encoded as URLs, such as DOIs.
- *Accessibility*: Ongoing work to build general Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) solutions, such as in EOSC, as well as on developing the W3C specifications Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) and Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV).
- *Interoperability & Reuse* was broken down into descriptions of structure, semantics and context.
 - Structural descriptions of data are often part of domain standards and proprietary formats but there are only a few standards for use across domains or technologies, such as the soon to be released DDI Cross Domain Integration (DDI-CDI) specification that specifically address cross-domains issues. But also more narrow specifications, such as

the W₃C specifications CSV on the web, Data Cube Vocabulary, Metadata Vocabulary for Tabular Data.

- Semantic descriptions of data include many domain-specific ontologies and vocabularies but there are generic and developing standards for geography, time, units of measurement, description of concepts and their relations (OWL, RDF, SKOS, XKOS). There are also examples of “semantic bridges”, such as OBO Foundry/BioPortal and Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM).
- Contextual descriptions of data traditionally rely on implicit knowledge in the domain. There are standards for describing provenance and processing, such as W₃C PROV Ontology (PROV-O), its PROV-ONE data specific profile, and SDTL and VTL for describing processing functions. And ongoing work is addressing how to describe measurements or observations, such as I-ADOPT.
- There are also some standards for managing resources (purpose, usage, cost/benefit) that could be considered such as Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) and the UN/ECE Generic Activity Model for Statistical Organisations (GAMSO).

II. The Structural Description of Data: DDI-CDI and the Variable Cascade

[DDI-CDI](#) is a model and a specification designed to support cross-domain data production activities. It integrates and can function as a bridge across standards/models (SKOS, Schema.org, DCAT, PROV-O, SDMX, etc) and it covers descriptions of data structures/content, processing and provenance, as well as variables, classifications and concepts etc.

Four larger parts of the model were highlighted: 1) The variable cascade provides conceptual, represented and instance level descriptions of the variables that the data provides values for; 2) Data organisation describes datasets with corresponding data structures, data points and datums; 3) Concepts and representations links variables to domain concepts and vocabularies; and 4) Process description to that provides descriptions of how the other objects are used and produced.

The distinction between conceptual, represented and instance level descriptions can be used to compare and integrate data from different datasets by linking variables representing the same concept using different vocabularies or encoded differently across the datasets. The data descriptions also support linking across datasets with varying structures (wide, long, key–value, dimensional). Domain specific concepts and vocabularies are referenced and not built into the model, which makes the model extensible and useful across domains.

III. The Fully-Described Observation: ISO Observations, Measurements and Samples, together with Related Standards

[ISO/DIS 19156:2022](#) will be the next version of an existing standard and will cover observations, measurements and samples for a wide range of areas in relation to geographic information. The current version describes an observation’s corresponding feature of interest, observed property, procedures and resulting values. An upcoming update will include descriptions of the observer, host, time-based information and sampling/populations.

[The I-ADOPT \(InteroperABLE Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies\) framework](#) was developed by the RDA community and was highlighted as a way to systematically decompose a complex observed property (property X of object of interest Y contained in Z given constraint C) into parts that can be mapped to controlled terminologies and concepts to enable mappings across datasets.

IV. Looking Forward: Planned and Needed Work

Cross-domain interoperability was highlighted as an important aspect of addressing the International Science Council's (ISC's) Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) where CODATA is leading a 10-year programme titled [Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges](#). In that context the 2-year EC funded [WorldFAIR: Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice](#) project will focus on 11 domain and cross-domain case studies to address challenges in interoperability within disciplines and for interdisciplinary research—in line with the recommendations from the [Turning FAIR into Reality EC report](#) and the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#). The case studies will develop FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and test the ideas outlined in this session.